

A long-term archiving and dissemination ecosystem for Humanities' research data

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Introduction. For almost 20 years, the digital repository GAMS (Geisteswissenschaftliches Asset Management System) has been providing long-term preservation of Humanities' resources offering both a technical solution and a way of achieving sustainability in the handling of research data. Such domain-specific digital repositories rely on specialised design principles and a strategic orientation to balance the need for long-term sustainability and the use of advanced technologies. The repository solely relies on open source software due to its commitment to open access and open science. Its design principles intend to foster compliance with international best practices like the COAR Community Framework for Good Practices in Repositories (COAR 2020) and the certification guidelines of the CoreTrustSeal, and following the FAIR principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability. Long-term preservation entails migration to new software versions and reflecting advancements in technology as well as responding to security issues; increase in projects and services require a more elaborate and stable system architecture. This submission describes the conceptual framework and architecture of a large digital repository infrastructure that specialises in the preservation, management and presentation of research data in the Humanities, as well as the maintenance and migration of this exemplary research data ecosystem.

1 Introduction

Domain-specific digital repositories rely on specialised design principles and a strategic orientation to balance the need for long-term sustainability and the use of advanced technologies. This proposal describes the conceptual framework and architecture of GAMS (Geisteswissenschaftliches Asset Management System), a large digital repository infrastructure maintained by the Centre for Information Modelling – Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities (University of Graz) that specialises in the preservation, management and presentation of research data in the Humanities. Further, issues of maintenance and migration of this exemplary ecosystem are discussed.

For almost 20 years, the digital repository GAMS has been providing long-term preservation of Humanities' resources offering both a technical solution and a way of achieving sustainability in the handling of research data. Currently, the repository contains about 115.000 annotated digital objects in more than 60 projects. This ranges from digital scholarly editions or text collections (e.g. letters, medieval accounting books) to image collections (e.g. historical photographs and postcards) as well as digitised cultural heritage collections (e.g. archaeological artefacts or museum objects)¹.

2 Design Principles

The OAIS-compliant² repository follows a largely XML-based content strategy utilising domain-specific data models and recognised international standards³. All projects are realised within the same infrastructure, using a limited set of preferred formats and technologies to ensure maintainability over a long period.

One of the unique features is the management of digital resources as complex digital objects based on content models (classes) for specific research data types, including any number of data streams (properties), partly automatically generated metadata records and disseminators (methods), specified in the WSDL⁴. These disseminators are implemented as services in the sense of service-oriented architectures⁵.

¹ Zentrum für Informationsmodellierung 2021.

² Space Data Systems 2012.

³ TEI (TEI Consortium 2021), LIDO (ICOM 2010), SKOS (Miles and Bechhofer 2009), RDF (Brickley and Guha 2014), EDM (Europeana Foundation 2014), Dublin Core (Dublin Core Metadata Initiative 2014) etc.

⁴ Chinnici et al. 2007.

⁵ Erl 2016.

Pipeline configuration is available for data storage, metadata extraction and dissemination strategies. The digital representation of a medieval manuscript for example consists of descriptive, technical, structural and administrative metadata, a plurality of facsimiles, a TEI-encoded transcription, and RDF representations to support linked data. Methods bound to the object allow for synoptic presentations of multiple variants, visualizations and provide project specific search and analysis functions. Further content models for common Humanities' data are natively implemented in the infrastructure, examples are 3D, LIDO, SKOS/OWL/RDF, RTI, METS/MODS. All data streams and methods are stored and managed within a single completely self-descriptive object, addressable by a unique identifier, which offers significant advantages for preservation.

The ecosystem solely relies on open source software due to its commitment to open access and open science⁶. The design principles intend to foster compliance with international best practice like the COAR Community Framework for Good Practices in Repositories⁷ and certification guidelines (GAMS is currently certified with the CoreTrustSeal and as a CLARIN B-Centre), following the FAIR principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability⁸.

3 Migration: Reaching the next Level of the Infrastructure

Long-term preservation entails migration to new software versions and reflecting advancements in technology as well as responding to security issues; increase in projects and services require a more elaborate and stable system architecture.

The new version of the core system is based on Fedora 6, which implies a fundamental switch from the object-oriented paradigm to a linked data architecture based on the Linked Data Platform (LDP)

⁶ Core technologies are Fedora Commons (currently version 3, after migration version 6) (Lagoze et al. 2005) for storage and management of digital objects, Apache Lucene (Apache Software Foundation 2011-2021) and Apache Solr (Apache Software Foundation 2021) for full text search, Blazegraph Triplestore (Systap 2018) as graph database, RDF4J (Eclipse RDF4J 2021), PostgreSQL Database Server 1996-2016 as relational database, Spring (Spring 2021), Apache Cocoon (Apache Software Foundation 2008) as platform for web services used as object disseminators, and Loris IIIF Image Server (Stroop 2013-2015) to provide access to images via the IIIF Image API (Appleby 2012-2021).

⁷ COAR 2020.

⁸ Force 11 2011-2020.

specification⁹ and a stronger focus on restful APIs for services¹⁰. This change, especially the disappearance of the content model-based approach, posed considerable challenges¹¹. The former object-oriented model had to be adapted to the new graph-based model without violating existing data and interfaces. Special attention had to be paid to conservation and re-implementation of the interfaces already in use to guarantee that all surface components will function without adaptations. The system was massively overhauled at the infrastructure level. The individual service components now run in isolated Docker containers in a Kubernetes-driven cluster. This allows for better scaling and shorter downtimes. With regard to storage infrastructure the new version relies on Ceph, a redundant, distributed and almost infinitely scalable storage solution. The effective migration to the new version is scheduled for the second half of 2021 given that Fedora 6 was recently released¹².

4 Conclusion

Running a digital repository of complex data from the Humanities has to take into account that data and software changes over time. Deciding on a limited list of preferred formats and standards and choosing an appropriate underlying software are thus important factors with regard to long-term preservation and sustainable data curation. Replacing core components of the software infrastructure can be seen as the ultimate proof of a successful long-term strategy.

5 Bibliografie

Apache Software Foundation. 2008. Apache Cocoon.
<http://cocoon.apache.org/> (accessed 26 July 2021).

Apache Software Foundation. 2011-2021. Apache Lucene.
<http://lucene.apache.org/> (accessed 26 July 2021).

Apache Software Foundation. 2021. Apache Solr.
<https://solr.apache.org/> (accessed 26 July 2021).

⁹ Speicher, Arwe and Malhotra 2015.

¹⁰ Fielding 2000.

¹¹ DuraSpace 2016.

¹² Lyrasis 2021.

- Appleby, M., Sanderson, R., Snyderman, S., Stroop, J. and Warner, S. 2012-2021. IIIF Image API 2.0. <http://iiif.io/api/image/2.0/> (accessed 26 July 2021).
- Brickley, D., Guha, R. V. 2014. RDF Schema 1.1. <https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-schema> (accessed 26 July 2021).
- Chinnici, R., Moreau, J., Ryman, A. and Weerawarana, S. 2007. Web Services Description Language (WSDL) Version 2.0. <https://www.w3.org/TR/wsdl20/> (accessed 26 July 2021).
- Confederation of Open Access Repositories (COAR). 2020. COAR Community Framework for Good Practices in Repositories. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4110829> (accessed 26 July 2021).
- Dublin Core Metadata Initiative. 2014. DCMI Metadata Terms. <http://dublincore.org/documents/dcmi-terms> (accessed 26 July 2021).
- DuraSpace. 2016: Design - API Extension Architecture. <https://wiki.duraspace.org/display/FF/Design+-+api+extension+architecture> (accessed 26 July 2021).
- Eclipse RDF4J 2021: Scalable RDF for Java <https://rdf4j.org/> (accessed 26 July 2021).
- Erl, T. 2016. Service-Oriented Architecture: Analysis and Design for Services and Microservices. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- Europeana Foundation. 2014. Europeana Data Model Documentation. <https://pro.europeana.eu/page/edm-documentation> (accessed 26 July 2021).
- Fielding, R.T. 2000. Architectural Styles and the Design of Network-based Software Architectures. Ph.D. thesis, University of California, Irvine.

- Force 11. 2011-2020. The Fair Data Principles.
<https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>
(accessed 26 July 2021).
- ICOM. international committee for documentation. 2010.
Lightweight Information Describing Objects – LIDO.
<http://network.icom.museum/cidoc/working-groups/lido/lido-technical/specification/> (accessed 26 July 2021).
- Lagoze, C., Payette, S. and Shin, E. 2005. Fedora: An architecture for complex objects and their relationships, Berlin-Heidelberg,
<http://arxiv.org/ftp/cs/papers/0501/0501012.pdf>
(accessed 26 July 2021).
- Lyrasis. 2021. Fedora 6.0.0.
<https://duraspace.org/fedora/download/> (accessed 26 July 2021).
- Miles, A. and Bechhofer, S. 2009. SKOS Simple Knowledge Organization System Reference. In: W3C (eds.).
<https://www.w3.org/TR/2009/REC-skos-reference-20090818> (accessed 26 July 2021).
- Speicher S., Arwe J., Malhotra, A. 2015. Linked Data Platform 1.0.
<https://www.w3.org/TR/ldp/> (accessed 26 July 2021).
- Spring 2021: <https://spring.io/> (accessed 26 July 2021).
- Stroop, J. et al. 2013-2015. Loris IIF Image Server.
<https://github.com/loris-imageserver/loris> (accessed 26 July 2021).
- Systap. 2018. Blazegraph. <https://www.blazegraph.com>
(accessed 26 July 2021).
- TEI Consortium. 2021. TEI P5: Guidelines for Electronic Text Encoding and Interchange. Version 4.2.2. <https://www.tei-c.org/Vault/P5/4.2.2/doc/tei-p5-doc/en/html/> (accessed 26 July 2021).

The PostgreSQL Global Development Group. 1996-2016.
PostgreSQL 9.1.24 Documentation.
<https://www.postgresql.org/docs/9.1/index.html>
(accessed 26 July 2021).

The Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems. 2012.
Reference Model for an Open Archival Information
System (OAIS).
<https://public.ccsds.org/pubs/650x0m2.pdf> (accessed
26 July 2021).

Zentrum für Informationsmodellierung – Austrian Centre for
Digital Humanities. 2021. GAMS.
Geisteswissenschaftliches Asset Management System.
<http://gams.uni-graz.at> (accessed 26 July 2021).